

Distribution of SC Population in Solapur District: A Geographical Analysis

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Abstract:-

The present paper has been attempted to study, 'Distribution of SC Population in Solapur District: A Geographical Analysis'. Population distribution refers to the way in which the members of a population or of a specified subgroup of a population are dispersed physically in a specific area. There are three types of population distribution which are a uniform, random, or clumped pattern. Uniform means that the population is evenly spaced, random indicates random spacing, and clumped means that the population is distributed in clusters. Population distribution is a measure of how spread out a population is in any given area. The simplest way to measure population distribution is to calculate the percentage of a population over a specific geographic area.

Population distribution on a global scale is highly uneven. The main factors determining population distribution are climate, landforms, topography, soil, energy and mineral resources, accessibility like distance from sea coast, natural harbours, navigable rivers or canals, cultural factors, political boundaries, controls on migration and trade, government policies, types of economic activities, technology including type of farming and transportation facilities, social organization. demographic factors like changes in natural increase and migration are also effects on population distribution.

The adverse physical conditions and lack of sufficient opportunities for means of livelihood have been mainly responsible for discouraging inhabitation in certain areas. Climatic conditions are perhaps the most important of all the geographic influences on population distribution. Apart from physical factors several social, demographic, economic, political and historical factors affect population distribution.

The Scheduled Castes (SCs) and Scheduled Tribes (STs) are officially designated groups of people and among the most disadvantaged socio-economic groups in India. The terms are recognized in the Constitution of India and the groups are designated in one or other of the categories. For much of the period of British rule in the Indian subcontinent, they were known as the Depressed Classes.

The present paper mainly focused on the distribution of SC population in Solapur district. In the Solapur district SC population was 238837 (12.84%) in the year 1961, while in the year 2011, the SC population was 649745 (15.05%). In the tehsil wise study the highest SC population in percentage was seen in the Malshiras tehsil, while lowest SC population seen in South Solapur tehsil.

Keywords: SC Population (Scheduled Castes Population).

1. Introduction:

It is observed that the SC population distributed in Solapur district is uneven. Population distribution is a measure of how spread out a population is in any given area. Population distribution denotes the spatial pattern due to dispersal of population, formation of agglomeration, linear spread etc. Population density is the ratio of people to physical space. It shows the relationship between a population and the size of the area in which it lives. The simplest way to measure population distribution is to calculate the percentage of a population over a specific geographic area.

The concepts of population distribution and density are so closely related to each other that it would be appropriate to

discuss them together though the two concepts are different. Population distribution is based on location while density is a ratio. Population distribution denotes the spatial pattern due to dispersal of population, formation of agglomeration, linear spread etc. Population density is the ratio of people to physical space. It shows the relationship between a population and the size of the area in which it lives.

The main factors determining population distribution are climate, landforms, topography, soil, energy and mineral resources, accessibility like distance from sea coast, natural harbours, navigable rivers or canals, cultural factors, political boundaries, controls on migration and trade, government policies etc.

Since the independence of India, the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes were given Reservation status, guaranteeing political representation, preference in promotion, quota in universities, free and stipend education, scholarships, banking services, various government schemes and the constitution lays down the general

principles of positive discrimination for SCs and STs.

In the Solapur district SC population was not evenly distributed. The highest SC population was seen in the Malshiras tehsil, while lowest SC population seen in South Solapur tehsil.

2. Study Area:-

Solapur district is one of the important districts in Maharashtra. It lies entirely in the Bhima-Sina-Man basins. The district of Solapur is located between 17° 10' North and 18° 32' North latitudes and 74° 42' East and 76° 15' East longitudes. The East-West length of the district is about 200 kilometer and North-South width is about 150 kilometer. The total geographical area of the Solapur district is about 14895 square kilometer and population is 43,17,756 according to 2011 census. In term of area, Karmala is the largest tehsil and the lowest is North Solapur tehsil in the Solapur district. Solapur district plays significant role

in the fields of agriculture, economics, industrial and social fields. (Fig. No.1)

3. Objective:-

The important objective of the present research paper is as follows
To study the distribution of SC Population in Solapur District

4. Database and Methodology:-

The present paper depends on the secondary data. It has been collected through District Census Handbook, Social Economic Review and other materials used. The study has been concentrated in the spatial distribution of SC population in Solapur district. Some other sources of information are used for the present research, like unpublished material.

The collected information from the different sources is processed and percentage calculated. Final results are presented in the

form of tables with help of these tables different diagrams, graphs are made and analyzed.

5. Growth of SC Population in Solapur District:-

Table No.1
Growth of SC Population in Solapur District

Sr. No.	Year	Total Population	SC Population	% of SC Population
1.	1961	1860102	238837	12.84
2.	1971	2254369	320300	14.21
3.	1981	2588139	370468	14.31
4.	1991	3231057	497913	15.41
5.	2001	3849543	578123	15.02
6.	2011	4317756	649745	15.05

Source: Socio-Economic Abstract of Solapur District, 2013

Population growth refers to the change in the number of inhabitants of a territory over a specific period of time. Population growth is expressed either in terms of percentage or absolute numbers. It can be positive as well as negative.

Fig. No. 2

In the year 1961, the total population of Solapur district was 1860102, while the SC population was 238837 (12.84%). The next decade, 1971 the SC population was 320300(14.21%). In the year 2011, the total population of Solapur district was 4317756, while the SC population in same year 649745 (15.05%). It has been conclude that the total population as well as SC population in Solapur district in study period increased. Because of various positive initiative by government like health facility the population has been increased.

6. Distribution of SC Population in Solapur District:-

The way in which people are spread across the earth surface is known as the pattern of population distribution. Population distribution is a measure of how spread out a population is in any given area. The simplest way to measure population distribution is to calculate the percentage of a population over a specific geographic area.

Table No. 2
Distribution of SC Population in Solapur District, 2011

Sr. No	Name of Tehsil	Total Population	SC Population	% Of SC Population
1.	Karmala	254489	35217	13.84
2.	Madha	324027	46778	14.44
3.	Barshi	342711	50621	13.58
4.	North Solapur	1057352	155201	14.68
5.	Mohol	276920	42446	15.33
6.	Pandharpur	442368	68184	15.41
7.	Malshiras	485645	88581	18.24
8.	Sangola	322845	47322	14.66
9.	Mangalwedha	205932	31384	15.24
10.	South Solapur	260897	35151	13.47
11.	Akkalkot	314570	48860	15.53
	District Total	4317756	649745	15.05

Source: Socio-Economic Abstract of Solapur District, 2013

It has been observed that the uneven distribution of SC population in the study region. The table no. 2 shows the proportion of SC population is 15.05 per cent Solapur district, but their distribution varies from tahsil to tahsil. The high proportion of SC population to the total population is recorded in Malshiras due to the diversified tahsil in the study region. The moderate proportion of SC population to the total population is registered in Mohol, Pandharpur, Mangalwedha and Akkalkot tahsils. While, the low proportion of SC population to total

population has been seen in Karmala, Madha, Barshi, North Solapur, Sangola and South Solapur tahsils. It has been seen that various physical as well as socio-economic factors are responsible for the distribution of SC population in the study region.

Conclusion:-

Population growth has been refers to the change in the number of inhabitants of a territory over a specific period of time. Population growth is expressed either in terms of percentage or absolute numbers. It can be positive as well as negative.

Fig. No. 3

In the year 2011, the total population of Solapur district was 4317756, while the SC population in same year 649745 (15.05%). It has been concluded that the total population as well as SC population in Solapur district in study period increased. Because of various positive initiatives by government like health facility the population has been increased.

Population distribution is a measure of how spread out a population in any given area. The simplest way to measure population distribution is to calculate the percentage of a population over a specific geographic area. The regional disparity was observed in distribution of SC population in the Solapur district. In the Solapur district, the highest SC population was seen in the Malshiras tehsil that is 88581, while the lowest SC population seen in the Mangalvedha tehsil that is 31384. But in percentage the lowest SC population seen the South Solapur tehsil. It has been seen that various physical as well as socio-economic factors are responsible for the distribution of SC population in the study region.

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